

GENDER EQUALITY: ACHIEVEMENTS ACHIEVED

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Since the first years of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, achieving equal rights for women and men in our country has had a special place in our country's policy. The fact that this equality is strengthened and guaranteed by law in our Constitution, adopted in 1992, is a clear proof of this. The constitution is a solid foundation that guarantees the rights and freedoms of all members of our society as a source of our happiness. It is the time to develop and implement modern mechanisms to ensure equal rights. In fact, in recent years, important steps have been taken in our country to ensure gender equality and effective work has been carried out.

In order to strengthen the legal basis of human rights and freedoms, to further increase the active participation of women in the development of society, the attention to appointing them to responsible positions has increased.

The representation of women in parliament and local councils increased: women began to be appointed to local bodies of state administration, district governors.

Working bodies on gender equality issues were established in the Upper House of the Parliament. Legislation aimed at ensuring gender equality has been improved.

It should be noted separately that the long-awaited laws **"On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men"** and **"On protection of women from oppression and violence"** were adopted.

Adoption of the laws increased the opportunities for women to become active participants in the democratic processes implemented in our country. Protection of women's rights and interests As a result of the reforms carried out to ensure gender equality, the role of women in society is increasing.

In the fifth goal of sustainable development of Uzbekistan, similar tasks aimed at "Ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women" have been defined.

I was particularly pleased that the Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for ensuring gender equality in 2020-2030 was adopted

and that my proposals to this strategy were taken into account, as well as that I contributed to the reforms in the field of ensuring gender equality.

This Strategy allows us to form a respectful attitude towards human rights in the country, to further increase the prestige of Uzbekistan in the international arena, and at the same time to put our lagging work on the right track in the comprehensive protection of women.

The strategy emphasizes the support of women's right to equal access to economic resources, including real estate, land, financial loans, public funds, and freely chosen types of entrepreneurial activity.

In particular, tasks related to further improvement of programs for providing women with decent work in remote areas, expansion of women's right to employment and use of the labor market will lead to greater prosperity of families in our country.

Most importantly, in order to help the victims of violence, rehabilitation and adaptation of victims of violence, as well as taking necessary measures to further improve the activities of suicide prevention centers and women's entrepreneurship centers and bring their activities to a new level is one of today's urgent issues. .

Under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a lot of work is being done to ensure gender equality, as a result of which the active participation of women in all spheres of society is increasing.

The establishment of the Commission on Family and Women's Issues in the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, and the Commission on the Protection of Women and Girls and Gender Equality in the Senate under the initiative of the President, proves that the interests of women are always in focus in Uzbekistan.

Tanzila Norbaeva was elected for the first time in the history of our country at the suggestion of the President of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis and the chairman of the commission on issues of ensuring gender equality. Tanzila Norboeva is a leading woman with extensive life experience working in the public administration system. He became an active participant in many reforms implemented in our country during his working as the Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Chairman of the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan.

The countries of the world are becoming aware of the work being done to ensure gender equality in our country.

On September 23, 2020, the leader of our country gave a speech at the session of the United Nations General Assembly held in the form of a video conference on the 75th anniversary of the United Nations, while expressing his opinion on issues of regional and global importance, while also focusing on our policy to ensure gender equality in our country, he said, "Gender equality policy is a priority issue for us. The role of women in public administration is getting stronger. The number of female deputies in our new Parliament has doubled."

In fact, it is possible to see that the participation of women in all spheres of society is increasing day by day in our country.

It is no secret that the activity of women is stronger than that of men in educational institutions and spiritual and educational activities.

A number of laws have been adopted to further strengthen gender equality in Uzbekistan. Including 2019

Chapter 7, adopted by the Legislative Chamber on August 17, approved by the Senate on August 23, consists of 32 articles "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" and 35 articles "Protection of women from oppression and violence" "On" entered into force.

According to these documents, not recognizing the equal rights and freedoms of men and women in all spheres of our country's life, distinguishing, denying or restricting their equality is direct discrimination based on gender.

The laws on guarantees of equal rights for women and men state that women and men have equal rights in the management of state and community affairs, electoral processes, education and research in science, work and social protection, as well as in all spheres of society and state life. equal participation is guaranteed.

All the laws adopted to ensure gender equality are showing their results. Today, the number of women working in leadership positions in state and public organizations is increasing. The participation of women in the state management system is also increasing significantly. Today, 32% of the deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, and 32% of the senators

25 percent are women.

Tanzila Norboeva, chairwoman of the Commission on Gender Equality, speaking at the United Nations Global Summit on Women, emphasized that gender equality is being ensured in our country, and

the law on guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men is widely implemented.

Today, the laws adopted in our country on ensuring gender equality are being widely implemented in life, great progress is being made in this field, it is also recognized by international organizations, including the permanent representative of the United Nations Organization in Uzbekistan, Helena Fraser, noted that important steps are being taken to ensure gender equality in Uzbekistan.

He pointed out that a number of legal documents adopted in Uzbekistan on gender equality, including the Decree of the head of our country on ensuring women's rights, protecting women from violence against them, supporting women's entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship, within the framework of cooperation between representatives of the United Nations in Uzbekistan The establishment of a special group on issues of gender equality will serve to increase the prestige of Uzbekistan in international circles.

International experts dealing with issues of gender equality believe that Uzbekistan serves as an example for other countries in terms of protecting the rights and interests of women. According to them, Uzbek women are occupying leading positions in many fields due to their knowledge, experience, qualifications and skills. Uzbekistan's work and achievements in ensuring gender equality are studied within the framework of organizations such as the United Nations, the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, and the Commonwealth of Independent States.

Distribution of information materials on the topic "Social protection of women - one of the priorities of trade unions of Uzbekistan" among the 193 member countries of the United Nations in New York, in which special attention is paid to ensuring the rights and interests of women in Uzbekistan today, women's social and political activities increase, highlighting that social, economic, and legal protection of women is one of the priority areas of state policy, proves that Uzbekistan's work on gender equality can be a model for other countries.

Many international experts studying the issue of gender equality pay great attention to the study of Uzbekistan's policy in this field. The chairman of the National Council of Women's Organizations of the USA, President of the Institute of Women's Studies and Training, Susan Skanala, said that the measures taken to protect women's rights in Uzbekistan deserve a high rating.

"Pulse UK" newspaper, published in Great Britain, published a special article on the topic of gender equality on its page. In it, it is highlighted that the most proud place is given to women in Uzbekistan, that all conditions have been created to improve their activities and develop their creative and spiritual potential.

The achievements of Uzbekistan in terms of gender equality have been widely covered in the Chinese "DunfanTszabao" and Kuwaiti "Times Kuwait" newspapers, in the reports of international experts such as Evgenia Makhmutova, associate professor of the applied political science department of the Finance University under the Russian government, V. Kulik, director of the Ukrainian Civil Society Problems Research Center.

According to the representatives of many international organizations and international experts, the progress achieved by Uzbekistan in terms of gender equality can serve as an example for many countries.

In Uzbekistan, under the leadership of the President, all conditions are being created to ensure gender equality, support women in every way, and realize their dreams.

The work being carried out in our country to ensure gender equality proves that it has really risen to the level of state policy. Such a policy is one of the positive results of the reforms implemented by our country in the field of human rights.

The ongoing work on ensuring gender equality will serve as a solid foundation for the economic, social, political and spiritual development of our country in the future.

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